

Decommonization-commonization dynamics and social movements: insights from a meta-analysis of case studies

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Abstract

According to some authors, the sustainability of community-based natural resource management systems depends on the to mobilize against external threats and participate in social movements. In this paper we explore the validity of the conjecture via a meta-analysis of case studies where local resource use communities have mobilized against decommonization threats. In that aim, we first characterize the drivers of said threats and the way they impact essential characteristics of the commons management. Then we assess the extent to which the social movements contribute to “commonization” processes. As we found, although the impacts of “decommonization” drivers on CBNRM regimes and communities justify the participation of communities in social movements, the (positive) impact of these movements on said regimes and communities goes beyond those grievances.

1. Introduction

The international research on the benefits of community-based natural resource management (CBNRM) regimes to achieve sustainable development has come along with concerns about the vulnerability of said regimes to globalization, shortsighted government regulations, marginalization, intensified land competition from commercial interests for resource extraction, and other global political economy threats (Salvanes and Squires 1995, Blaikie 2006, Baynes et al. 2015, Notess et al. 2018). Increasing attention has been paid to the participation of local communities in social movements against those threats (Anguelovski and Martínez Alier 2014). Communities' capacity to manage natural resources via CBNRM regimes and mobilize for the promotion or defense of said regimes are two sides of the same collective action phenomenon (Scholtens 2016); however, they have so far been studied rather separately by scholars. Little is known, therefore, about whether and how mobilization contributes to better CBNRM. In this chapter, we address that question via a meta-analysis of 81 cases around the world (see Villamayor-Tomas and Garcia-Lopez 2018 for methodological details). The research questions of the study are: Which threats jeopardize the sustainability of CBNM regimes beyond the ability of their members to self-organize, and how? How do social movements contribute in turn to the robustness of said CBNRM?

Some works have highlighted the intricate connections between social movements (such as those against extractive industries or large conservation areas) and the formalization of customary community-based management regimes (Perreault 2001, Alcorn et al. 2003, Gerber 2011, Veuthey and Gerber 2012, Kashwan 2017); the recognition of collective territorial rights (Conde and Kallis 2012, Kurien 2013); and the reinvigoration of local indigenous practices and knowledge (Armitage 2005, Poole 2005). Underlying these works is the understanding that local resource-dependent communities may “organize and fight for preserving their means of

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livelihood in the name of social justice, defence of customary territorial rights, health, or sacredness”, a process which could “eventually allow them to renegotiate power distribution” (Veuthey & Gerber, 2012, p. 612). Apart from defending existing CBNRM initiatives, the struggles can also lead to the creation and or formalization of new initiatives. That is precisely the case of landless peasant movements and the creation of self-organized communities for the management of newly-acquired lands (Diegues 1998, Lynn 1998), or the activities carried by irrigation, fishery and forest movements to create extractive reserves and co-management agreements (Kurien 1991, Paudel et al. 2010, Verzijl et al. 2017).

This chapter focuses on movements as drivers of “commonization” processes. “Commonization” and “decommonization” can be understood as two sides of the same “CBNRM coin”. ‘Commonization’ is understood as a “process through which a resource gets converted into a jointly used resource under commons institutions that deal with excludability and subtractability, and ‘decommonization’ refers to a process through which a jointly used resource under commons institutions loses these essential characteristics” (Nayak and Berkes 2011, pp. 133). From this perspective, CBNRM regimes can be understood as outcomes/manifestations of “commonization” processes as well as vulnerable to “decommonization” processes. Both processes reoccur over time simultaneously as they are influenced by the prevalent social, economic, political and ecological drivers (Nayak and Berkes 2011).

“Decommonization” processes can be associated to the constraints imposed onto local common-pool resource governance systems by states’ enclosures policies (De Angelis 2012), recentralization policies (Ribot et al., 2006), ‘fortress’ conservation policies (Brockington 2002), or elite capture and inequalities (Blaikie 2006, Persha and Andersson 2014). “Commonization” processes, on the other hand, can be associated to certain institutional design principles (Ostrom 1990, Cox et al. 2010), devolution of management rights and co-management (Pomeroy and Berkes 1997, Moreno-Sánchez and Maldonado 2010), and participatory/collaborative processes (Koontz 2004, Lubell 2005).

The study of social movements contributes to understand the connection between “decommonization” and “commonization”. As illustrated above, the very impact of “decommonization” drivers constitutes in many cases the motivation for communities to mobilize socially and participate in social movements. In the rest of the chapter presents results of the meta-analysis in detail following that logic.

2. Decommonization drivers

The content analysis resulted in 16 different drivers of decommonization, which can be classified in to larger groups associated to conservation policy, economic policy, political policy, the actions of large scale users, the actions of small users.

Figure 1. Frequency* of decommunization drivers

*Although the number of cases include in the study is 81, multiple impacts were recorded per case.

Note: in green: conservation policy; red: economic policy; dark blue: large scale users; light blue: small users; yellow: political policy; grey: other.

Natural resource management policy: Failed decentralization

This driver is illustrated mostly by forests cases where the use of decentralization policies by central governments are actually used to restrict local autonomy (ribot...). This can occur via de imposition of particular organizational structures and priorities that structure local decision making, or the definition of certain rules for the disbursement of funds that give priority to some local organizations over others (Alcorn 2003, Springate et al. 2008, Garcia-Lopez and Antinori 2018).

As pointed by Alcorn for the case of Adat communities in India, the approval by the end of the 1990s of regulations ostensibly to empower adat institutions at local government level, translated in “a new set of manufactured adat institutions, in effect changing the definition of adat in national discourse frames and undermining indigenous adat autonomy and authority” (Alcorn 2003). In Mexico, a new program to strengthen self-governance by forest communities (PROFAS) in 2004 forced communities “to adopt a specific legal structure (regional association of forest-users, ARS), with a bylaw, provided by the government, which enumerated the list of activities, mostly focused on technical forestry activities”. (Garcia-Lopez and Antinori 2018)

As pointed also by Springate (2008) for the case of India, “Joint Forest Management policies emerged at the end of the 1980s as a means to induce local people to help in the forest departments’ regeneration efforts, through legitimating their NTFP collection and offering them a share of the ‘major produce’ on final felling in return for help in protection. Wage labour opportunities were sometimes also provided (from donor funds). However rights were not provided and forest departments have often used the programmes as instruments to extend their authority structures to the village, generate funds from donors to expand their staffing and even take more lands from local people through enforcing no cultivation on JFM plots.” (Springate 2008)

Natural resource management policy: Scientific, top-down conservation measures

This driver speaks about the well-known tendency of governments to design natural resource management policies that ignore local knowledge and practices, frequently upon the exclusive basis of science-based knowledge (Agrawal...).

This can occur in post-colonial contexts, as a result of the formation of new governments or in the aftermath of political transitions. In Alaska, the state “assumed jurisdiction over all marine mammal species not covered by international treaties (such as gray and bowhead whales and fur seals) in 1960. The state asserted its authority by establishing and enforcing seasons,

bag limits, and methods (...) and also established programs of scientific research on the status and characteristics of the mammals. The state regime was implemented however, without regard to unextinguished yet judicially and legislatively recognize Alaskan Native hunting and fishing rights” (Langdon 1989, pp. 156).

Scientific top-down conservation measures, can also be motivated by economic concerns, like in the case of lobster regulations in the late 1960s in Southwest Nova Scotia (Kearney 1989), where standard trap limits were established by the federal government to reduce “the total cost of fishing effort and hence increasing the net incomes of fishermen (Kearney 1989, pp.90)”.

A quite paradigmatic specification of this driver is also the creation of conservation areas, such as the Mayan Biosphere Reserve (Cronkleton 2008, Paudel 2010), the Cayos Cochinos Marine Protected Area (Brondo Brown 2011), or the Serengeti National Park (Neumann 1995). In some cases, the areas are well intended and informed but lack appropriate implementation resources. In Honduras, the government-promoted Cayo Cochinos Protected Area failed short of successfully combining marine protection and community livelihood sustainability; “without the personnel and resources in government agencies to successfully manage the enlarged responsibility, management of natural resources was literally auctioned off to private enterprises and NGOs, diverting profits from natural resources away from local communities and toward elite and foreign interests” (Brondo Brown 2001, pp. 95).

In most of the cases, however, good intentions have been offset by the failure to recognize the complexity of the socio-ecological environment upon which they are imposed. In Guatemala, the design of the Mayan Biosphere Reserve “did not take into adequate account the complexity of the region’s pre-existing diverse population and natural resource-use patterns. On the contrary, bans and other restrictions on usage were originally imposed on populations both within the reserve and in its surrounding buffer zones” (Cronkleton 2008, p. 6).

Privatization

This driver speaks about the numerous initiatives carried by governments to enclose resources into private property rights, including just use or also exclusion and alienation rights (Schlager and Ostrom 1993). This has been frequently done under the assumptions that customary land is being used in an unproductive fashion or not used at all; and that private property right regimes can promote a balance between capital investments in productivity (and therefore economic growth), as well as sustainable management. In Malawi, the official stand on land tenure issues in Malawi since colonial rule has been that private ownership and statutory security represent a desired trajectory to rural development (Chinsinga 2008; Chirwa 2004). Consequently, customary land is perceived as a reserve from which private and public land ownership should be created. In this process, the state’s responsibility is to document, classify and approve land lease through the Minister responsible for land. For instance, between 1991 and 1997, 1.20 million hectares of customary land were transferred to private and public land ownership following this approval process (Chinsinga et al. 2013, pp. 1070).

Also, privatization is done ex-ante via property law (see above), or ex-post via the legalization of illegal enclosures. In Mexico the government recently proposed to amend the law to “allow confiscation of land by the state on behalf of private industries and to introduce only cash compensation instead of providing new land for resettlement and cultivation” (Randeria 2003, pp. 48). And in Ecuador, the Correa government revised the Constitution and signed a decree to authorize the legalization of illegally established ponds for shrimp farming in community coastal mangroves (Veuthey and Gerber 2012, pp. 616).

In many occasions privatization also includes the transferability of rights via markets. The underlying assumption is and that such transferability can contribute to efficient allocation of the resources (i.e., to uses that make the most value of them) under changing conditions. In New Zealand, one of the results for fisheries management of the new Labour government reform in the mid-1980s was “the privatization of natural resources, particularly forests and fisheries.

This led to the creation of the Quota Management System (QMS) and the allocation of Individual Transferable Quotas (ITQs) to those who could demonstrate recent commercial participation in a fishery. Ownership of ITQs granted a share in an annually determined total catch for each fishery. Under the QMS, anyone who wanted to fish commercially had to own or lease quota, as well as a fishing boat (De Alesi 2012, 400).

Corporate-oriented policy

This driver consists most paradigmatically on governmental reforms to open the economies to foreign investment and facilitate capital investments. In Mexico, the culmination of one such reform was the signature in the 1994 North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), which “eliminated commercial tariffs for timber such that Mexican timber faced stiffer competition from plantation-style industries” from multi-nationals. (Garcia Lopez and Antinori 2018, pp. 198-199).

Also paradigmatic are the use of subsidies and programs by the government to promote intensive, market-oriented resource use. In Chile, the forest industry expanded notably from the mid-70’s on after the approval of Decree 701. “This decree stipulated that the State would subsidize 75 percent of the cost of plantations on lands qualified as preferably suitable for forestation (in some cases up to 90 per cent was subsidized). The State also contributed to concentrating the ownership of the land and tree plantations, through the privatization of public land and of state company land at very low prices” (Montalba Navarro 2005, pp. 21). Similarly, in India, the “Indo-Norwegian Project for Fisheries and Fishermen Community Development (INP), initiated in Quilon district in 1953, had four components. It upgraded technology by introducing new craft-gear combinations, mainly trawlers and purse-seine nets. It built onshore infrastructure such as fish landing centres, curing yards, ice plant and cold storage, and a trawler repair workshop. It organized fishers into cooperatives, which also disseminated loans and training” (Sinha 2012, pp. 374).

State concessions and projects

Another important driver are government concession and tax-financed projects. Long term concessions aim at providing security to large scale investors and/or guarantee their market share. In Mexico, “the transformation of the Fisheries Law in 1992 eliminated cooperatives’ exclusive fishing rights and provided greater security for investors by extending the aquaculture concession period from twenty-five to fifty years, openly encouraging private investment” (Altamiano and Jimenez 2017, pp. 3); and the granting of integrated logging and processing industries monopsonistic rights over extensive areas was complemented with regulations that allowed communities to sell logging right only to those industries (Klooster 2000)

State projects are usually branded by the government as measures to increase resource productivity, in many cases to benefit powerful interest groups or industries. The Independencia Aqueduct project in Northern Mexico, for example, transferred water from the Yaqui Valley to the coastal city of Hermosillo, reflecting “a shift in the regional axis of power from its old hub—the agroindustrial Yaqui Valley—to urban and industrial Hermosillo” (Radonic 2015, p. 35).

Large scale users

Another quite important threat is the advent of large scale users, which can be classified into “large scale competitors” such as timber firms, fishing trawlers, and “large scale acquisitions and projects” such as plantations, and mining, oil and other energy projects. In a few case cases the presence of large companies can be traced back to colonial times or authoritative governments (Pinkerton 1993, Brownhill 2007, Powell 2017), while in a number of others it is linked to more recent governmental reforms and development policy (Zoe 2013, Altamiano and Jimenez 2017, Garcia-Lopez and Antinori 2018).

In some cases, the intrusion of large scale users is justified by the government on the basis that they are particularly able to make efficient use of the resources. That is the case, for

example, of the Limpasa Sugar Company in Mankhambira, Malawi, where “National level government officials particularly argue that the company is one way of productively utilizing the idle land that will help address critical foreign exchange shortages” (Chinsinga et al. 2013, pp. 1076); the cases of Canada and Southern India, where export-oriented industrialization became a key priority for state governments (Morell 1989, Sinha 2012, Somayahi 2017) . As pointed by Sinha (2012) the industry “generated revenue including foreign exchange on the one hand and increased the income of fishers and the protein intake of Kerala’s population on the other.” (pp. 373); or the case of Tañon Strait, Philippines, where government promoted massive oil exploration activities by multinational companies with the goal to achieve energy independence (Zoe 2013).

In other cases, the presence of large users is rather the result of spontaneous rent seeking from the part of said users. Those are the cases, for example, of Acre, in the Amazon, where there was a continuous concentration of land in the hands of a few large owners, cattle ranchers and other speculative holders since the 1970s and at least the mid-1990s (Diegues 1996); the case of big fishing trawlers crossing the Indian-Northern Sri Lankan borders during the war between the Sri Lankan army and the guerrilla forces; or the case of the development of prawn industry in Lake Chilika, India, first “by on-fishermen community in Chilika area started eyeing the lake for prawn. First the unscrupulous traders and middlemen, then the politicians with their musclemen, a handful of big business families of Orissa and their local middlemen termed as "mafia", and finally, the big industrial houses” (Pattanaik, 2003, pp. 57).

Finally, it is important to note the association of the large scale users driver to issues of elite capture and corruption dynamics. In Nigeria, “the state received oil revenues, which were massively channeled to corrupt politicians, civil servants, intermediaries, contractors and motley hanger” (pp. 32-33). And in Canada of the 1990s, “the major multinational timber companies, which leased Crown forests under long - term licence agreements, played a major role in the development of forest policy and guidelines for forest practices” (Pinkerton 1993, n.p.)

Small, heterogeneous users

A less visible but still disturbing driver is the arrival of small users in large numbers. These are in most cases non-subsistence users (i.e. commercial or recreational users), reside outside of the communities. As pointed by Nguiffo’s (1996) with regard to the Southern Cameroon forest sector “Poachers are professional hunters who live on selling their catch; they are not natives of the hunting grounds, and have no obligation of respect to the hunting grounds or to the rules for the hunting period or local hunting taboos. They hunt to satisfy the ever-growing demand from urban centres, not the limited demand of forest inhabitants (pp. 109). Like with large users, small users are motivated by rent seeking; however, they do necessarily count on the favor of governments as much as large users do, and just reflect gaps and contradictions in the implementation of development and conservation policies. In Ecuador, the growth of farmed shrimp over mangroves all cross Ecuador reflected “a blatant contradiction between the laws protecting the mangroves, and the practices on the ground. As a result, shrimp farming developed illegally with the implicit approval of the government as it would have been impossible to produce so much shrimp with so few concessions granted.” (Veuthey and Gerber 2012, pp. 614).

Inheritances from colonialism and autocratic governments

This driver speaks about the endurance of inheritances from colonial and/or autocratic governments in newly independent or democratized countries.

Those inheritances mean the perpetuation of certain stereotypes about rural, resource dependent communities. In Indonesia, the fall of Suharto’s regime, barely changed the colonial-inspired designation of rural communities as "isolated native groups" that need to be pushed from primitive livelihoods into civilization (Li 2004). As pointed by Li (2004) the new

government’s “official program designed to civilize such people views them as generic primitives, occupants of a tribal slot which is negatively construed. Their ethnic or tribal identities, cultural distinctiveness, livelihood practices, and ancient ties to the places they inhabit are presented in program documents as problems, evidence of closed minds and a developmental deficit that a well-meaning government must help them to overcome.” (pp. 344).

Similarly, inheritances may also mean the continuance of certain understandings of what “public domain” is, and certain modes of socio-economic organization. In Colombia, the central government considered the extensive mangrove areas in the southern part of the Pacific coast as ‘areas of public interest’ rather than community territory. (Oslender 2004). In El Tule village and many other rural areas in Mexico, the “Hacienda” model of agricultural exploitation (large scale, private plantation that provides employment to members of surrounding communities) has become socially accepted over time despite its colonial foundations (Lynn 1996).

Colonial inheritances also mean the perpetuation of certain management practices and forms of knowledge. In Tanzania, there has been “a distinct continuity between the colonial and post-colonial situations. The independent government has not significantly altered park and wildlife laws (...). African personnel are trained in practices developed in the west, and international conservation organizations still play a critical role.” (Neumann 1995, pp. 367).

Also, the driver manifests in the failed restitution of political rights of indigenous communities. In Peru, “successive democratic governments have failed to make progress in respecting and promoting the rights of indigenous peoples, especially the rights of the Mapuche. Under the Indigenous Pact (adopted in 1989), they have committed themselves to recognizing indigenous peoples (but) the government’s core policy has amounted to an ill-defined land restitution plan, combined with development programs and monetary compensation, the overall goal being to prevent an indigenous insurgency.” (pp. 3). In Canada, the 150-year plus effort of the Maori community “has resulted in limited Crown attempts to address historical grievances. There has also been limited recognition, in law, that the unique and valuable knowledge of Maori and their right to self-determination must be protected.” (Rixecker 2003, pp. 256)

3. Decommonization impacts, or the motivation for social mobilization

The above decommonization drivers had different impacts on resource dependent communities, which can be classified in to larger groups related to livelihood, rights, externalities, and culture and norms (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Frequency* of cases per type of impact

*Although the number of cases include in the study is 81, multiple impacts were recorded per case. Note: In red: livelihood related impacts; in blue: right-related impacts; in green: externality related impacts; in yellow: culture and norms-related impacts; in grey: other.

Dispossession

The most frequent impact faced by communities is the total loss of access to the resource. The resource may just be enclosed by individuals or granted in concession to the highest bidder (Montalba Navarro 2005; Correia 2010; Turner and Brownhill 2003); encroached by competing users like large timber companies or fishing trawlers (Cronkleton 2008, De Alesi 2012 Diegues 1996); devoted to new uses like in the transformation of forest land to large plantations (Alcorn 2003, Fradejas 2015, Chinsinga et al. 2013), energy and transport projects (Altamiano and Jimenez 2017, Correia 2010, Topatimasang 2005) or conservation areas (Randeria 2003, Paudel 2010, Roberts 2016); transferred from one territory to another, like in the case of water transfers (Radonic 2015); or become unusable due to flooding (Colchester 2005)

Also importantly, the process of dispossession comes with violations of political (e.g., consultation) rights and sometimes also violence. In Uganda, the Amuru Sugar project was possible thanks to the government's "usual arsenal of violence and bribery in an effort to evict local inhabitants and secure land for the company" (Martiniello 2013, pp. 660). In India, the Adviasi have been precluded from accessing their lands by more powerful groups and corporations, which use "a combination of cunningness, corruption, and violence to alienate people from the land" (Shock 2009, pp.190).

Resource use right restrictions

Another important impact are resource right restrictions. These can take the form of elimination of exclusive use rights, like in Mexico, where the "Fisheries Law in 1992 eliminated cooperatives' exclusive fishing rights and provided greater security for investors by extending the aquaculture concession period from twenty-five to fifty years" (Altamiano and Jimenez 2017); or in New Zealand, where the establishment of a Quota Management System served the purpose of formalizing but also limiting Maori's traditional use rights (De Alesi 2012).

Many restrictions are justified by governments and international organizations upon conservation goals but imposed in ignorance or disregard of local communities' customs and potential to act as stewards of the resource (Brondo Brown 2011, Cohen 1989, Cronkleton 2008, Poole 2005).

Control right restrictions

In some cases, the restriction of control rights manifest through the formal subordination of local authorities to higher level authorities. (Alcorn 2003, Brondo Brown 2011). In India, village governance law had priority over Adat rule; district governments had to give "their approval of the appointment of any new adat chief, whose powers have been restricted because the village group headman and the district head can intervene in his decisions." (Alcorn 2003, pp. 331). Similarly the Joint Forest Management program has been used by forest departments as an instrument to extend their authority structures to the village, generate funds from donors to expand their staffing (Springate 2008).

In some other cases, use rights are respected by default but community control is still not respected. The 1967 Maori Affairs Bill, for example, purported to improve conditions for Maori but maintained the compulsory sale of land owned by multiple Maori owners (De Alesi 2012). In Mexico, forest associations entitled to receive government support were required to adopt a specific legal structure which strengthened technical forestry capacities, restricted communal ownership (Garcia-Lopez and Antinori 2018). Previously, forest-owning communities maintained nominal control over forest land in these concessions, but they could only sell logging rights to the big industrial entities and they could not convert forests to other uses (Klooster 2000). In Colombia "Water Development Plans (WDPs) stated the government's intention to create economies of scale for water provision and to centralize water infrastructure,

management, and funding at the departmental, instead of municipal level, which vulnerated the autonomy of community aqueducts” (Pereira 2014, pp. 1998). More generally, the violation of community control rights manifests in the tendency of governments not to consult the communities in the elaboration of management plans when they should by law (Escobar 1998, Nguiffo 1996, Ohja 2011, Paudel 2010).

Displacement

Most reports of displacements correspond to resettlements. Many of these occur in the forest conservation context, where the “notion that forests and people cannot coexist implies that forest dwellers must be evicted in order to protect forested areas” (Roberts 2016, pp. 54).

Even if resettled communities are granted access to new resources, promised support for resettlement projects often proves inadequate (Cronkleton 2008, Montalba Navarro 2005). This is particularly clear in colonial contexts, like that affecting the Mapuche in Chile, where the communities have tended to be confined within “small spaces with marginal productive potential and ecologically of extreme fragility” (Montalba Navarro 2005, pp. 19). In other cases, like that of “riverine” communities in the Amazon, the families are just forced out of their lands and left on their own (Schwartzman 2010).

Livelihood loss

“Livelihood loss” is the second most frequently reported impact. This refers mostly to the loss of access to food, fodder for livestock, construction materials for houses or furniture, energy sources for heating or cooking (Brownhill 2007, Klooster 2000, Sinha 2012). This can be particularly hazardous for already poor communities because they are the most dependent on the commons (Martiniello 2013, Lynn 1996). As put by Kenney-Larzar (2012), “for a number of poorer households, the loss of forest resources was devastating because one of their only sources of income was logging timber from forested areas to build houses for wealthier families in the village”. In Bolivia, “the processing industry makes a significant contribution to Bolivia’s forest export earnings, but collection is still labour intensive, and nut gatherers remain some of the region’s poorest residents” (Paudel 2010). Similarly, women are also particularly vulnerable due to their central role they traditionally play in subsistence rural economies (Turner and Brownhill 2004).

The impact also relates to health issues (Rixecker 2003, Powell 2017). As pointed by Powell (2017) with regard to the Navajo community in North America, “the accumulated risks of environmental contamination from the extractive industry became increasingly evident. Asthma from airborne pollution, cancer from residual radiation, and vanishing aquifers and tributaries reshaped Dine landscapes and bodies into a sacrifice zone of the Southwest” (pp. 214)

The restriction of use due to expulsion or use right curtailments is the most evident way thorough which the loss of livelihood happens. As pointed by Brownhill (2007) “where industrial logging, mining, plantation agriculture, ranching, real estate development, manufacturing and private ‘game parks’ monopolize large areas of arable land, that land is no longer available for the production of food for local consumption. (pp. 3). Two other, less evident mechanisms are the conversion of community members into wage-laborers or their introduction into new resource use activities. The first mechanism precludes the community from capturing the full value of its member’s labor (Kenney-Lazar 2012). The second runs the risk of failure due to the difficulties encountered by users to adapt to the new activity. In India an “attempt to turn pastoralists into farmers failed due to the poor quality of land made available to families which had no knowledge of agriculture and no access to the inputs required for cultivation. Within a few years, many successful pastoralists, who had been selling milk and milk products over long distances, were reduced to wage labor” (Randeria 2003, pp. 43).

Cultural erosion

Colonization and certain government policies (e.g., conservation programs) can also have a negative impact on communities' cultural traits, such as collective identities, values, customs, and knowledge about livelihood practices (Cohen 1989, Alcorn 2003). As expressed by a Q'eqchi peasant with regard to the consolidation of large oil palm cultivations in the Sayaxché municipality (Guatemala), "our thinking is being dominated as well as our beliefs. This is the result of the way the powerful and rich people think. Of those who want to dispossess us from our lands once again." (Fradejas 2015, pp. 498).

Cultural erosion can in turn ease other decommodification processes and jeopardize the communities' survival. In New Zealand, the policy of "racial integration" during the 1950s and 1960s promoted the assimilation of urban life by the Maori community. As a result, "whole communities disappeared, and their marae now stand derelict or strangely desolated as first the young and their parents left to seek their fortunes in the new world" (Douglas, 1979, p. 103–109, cited in Sherman 2006).

Social capital distresses

Other important impacts that affect communities have to do with various secondary effects that manifest among community members in the form leadership corruption, women inequality, illegal resource use, and conflict. In San Martin, Mexico, timber smuggling in San Martin was just one minor symptom of an increasingly dysfunctional forest management system (...) concessions marginalized peasants from control over forests and from the benefits of forestry, and so the forest became, from their perspective, marginal. Alienated from their resources, they often resisted the system with tree theft, clearing, and burning" (pp. 291). In Makacoulibantang, India, most villagers do not want woodfuel being cut from surrounding forests but, "despite their objections, some village chiefs, who are usually hereditary powers appointed for life, allow production in village forests. Their decision is based partly on payoffs from merchants, and partly on the social status of merchants, which makes it difficult for chiefs to turn them down." (Ribot 2000, pp. 134).

Loss of organizational resources

Also, an important impact and reason for community mobilization is the "loss of organizational resources", due to the cancellation by the government of subsidies (De Alesi 2012), community development programs (Garcia-Lopez and Antinori 2018), or financial support for developing management plans (Stevens 2014).

Degradation externalities

Degradation externalities are also an important impact. These frequently occur in the interface between hydrological and aquatic systems and other resource systems. That is the case of hydrological systems that are polluted by substances from mining and oil extraction (Byambayav 2012, Hafild 2005, Stoltenbort 2016, Turner and Brownhill 2004, Urkidi 2010), massive deforestation (Pena 2003), or large-scale cultivations (Montalba Navarro 2005, Fradejas 2015). That is also the case of aquatic habitats suffering from siltation due to soil erosion connected to forest activities (Palmer 2017, Pinkerton 1993). In Mongolia, for example, "the environmental impact of placer gold mining in Orhon was deleterious. Many mines illegally diverted river streams and released dirty water into a river system. This caused extensive damage to local rivers such as the depletion and pollution of rivers (presence of sediment particles and nutrients)" (Byambayav 2012, pp. 18).

Also important although less frequent are the destruction and loss of species diversity due to aggressive harvest technologies in the context of large-scale logging (Ribot 2000), and fishing (Sinha 2012, Tang 2001). As described by Sinha (2012) for the case of fishing in Kerala, India, "trawlers derived their fishing technology from their origins as minesweepers in the

Second World War. These boats drag their nets along the seafloor, a technique that originally relied on depth-sounders and sonars developed during the Second World War and was later brought to a mass market”. As a result all foliage, rocky formations, sand towers and coral formations which contribute to fish reproduction were in effect destroyed (pp. 377). Mechanization unleashed a process of great ecological volatility.

Scarcity externalities

Scarcity externalities is also an important impact. Said externalities translated in a decreased the need of communities to invest more time and effort to obtain the same benefit from the resource, or just to decrease harvests. The most typical cases are illustrated by the actions of large-scale, industrial fishing firms which undermine the resource stock and/or its regeneration capacity (e.g., Jordan 1989, kurien 1991, Morrell 1989, Scholtens 2016, Sinha 2012,somayahi 2017). As pointed by Morrell with regard to fisheries in the Seekena River, Canada, “the vast majority of the catch of salmon and steelhead of Skeena origin is taken in mixed-stock ocean fisheries. Most stocks of Skeena salmon and steelhead are depressed below historical levels of abundance due primarily to overharvest in the industrial fisheries. Current production is dependent on a few strong stocks; this reduction in stock diversity increases the vulnerability of the system to run failures” (241-242). Also, scarcity externalities may occur despite the state recognition of communities’ rights. As pointed by Scholtens (2016) for the case of fisheries in North Sri Lanka, “North Sri Lankans now live in the ironic situation, that while enjoying fishing rights after 30 years of war, they are unable to really benefit from the Palk Bay resources’ in the face of a powerful trawler fleet” from Indian firms.

Secondarily but still importantly, the cases illustrate the connection with aggressive harvest techniques of small-scale non-subsistence users, like recreational and small commercial fishers (Langdon 1989, cohen 1989), or the “silent” impact of illegal forest poachers (Nguiffo 1996).

4. Commonization pathways though social movements

According to our findings, social movements contribute to communization via a number of pathways, which can be clustered in groups associated to the defense of communal rights and territories, the promotion of economic autonomy, the promotion of community human capital, the improvement of community decision making, the enhancement of community litigation capacities and the promotion of community organization (see Figure 3) (see also Villamayor-Tomas and Garcia-Lopez, 2018).

Figure 3. Frequency* of communalization pathways promoted by social movements

*Although the number of cases include in the study is 81, multiple impacts were recorded per case.

Note: In blue: defense of communal rights and territories; in yellow: promotion of economic autonomy; in green: promotion of community human capital; in red: improvement of community decision making; in grey: enhancement of community organization capacities.

Defense of communal rights and territories

By far, the most frequent pathway through which movements contribute to the clarification of social boundaries is defending community resource use and management rights. The defense of rights is indeed one of the main reasons behind the mobilization of communities and their participation in movements.

By claiming their resource use rights, the movements defend also the collective nature of such rights. In the Yaqui Valley, Mexico, the opposition to the *Independencia* water transfer has been a defense of the access to a resource on which people's livelihoods depend as much as "a fight over historical recognition of collective indigenous water rights" (Radonic, 2015, pp. 37). Also, many of the cases related to the defense of management rights are featured by indigenous communities, often under discourses of "self-determination" and autonomy (Escobar, 1998; Hoogesteger & Verzijl, 2015). A good number of them align with efforts to *formalize said rights in laws or constitutions*. For instance, in Mexico the struggles of forest communities against state and private timber concessions on their lands led to the passage of the 1986 Forest Law, which recognizes communities' forest management rights (Garcia-López & Antinori, 2018; Klooster, 2000).

Also, a recurrent outcome of pro-rights mobilizations is the creation and defense of *exclusive-use zones*, such as the "extractive forest reserves" promoted by the rubber tappers movement in Brazilian Amazon, and local forest communities in Petén, Guatemala (Cronkleton et al. 2008, Paudel et al. 2010); or the "trawler-free coastal fishing zones" reserved for artisanal fishing communities in Kerala and Goa, India (Kurien 1991, Sinha 2012). A related pathway is the *formalization of boundaries*, which takes place via the elaboration of maps (Diegues 1998, Alcorn et al. 2003, Roberts 2016), and the legal registration of the boundaries (Neumann 1995).

Promotion of economic autonomy

Movements also *add value to the participation of community members in CBNRM* regimes. This is accomplished by lobbying for tax benefits (Paudel et al. 2010) and attracting subsidies and development funds (Diegues, 1998; Garcia-López & Antinori 2018; Perreault, 2001), as well as by exploring new production strategies (Cronkleton et al., 2008), and facilitating access to markets and credit via information, diversification strategies and collective bargaining (Garcia-López & Antinori 2018; Lynn, 1998).

Also importantly, movements promote and support *community-based/grassroots development ventures*. Development ventures include community forestry enterprises for timber and non-timber products and ecotourism (Cronkleton et al., 2008; Diegues, 1998; Garcia-López & Antinori, 2018; Klooster, 2000); agricultural cooperatives (Diniz and Gilbert 2013); seed exchange networks and peasant-to-peasant market exchanges (Turner and Brownhill 2004, Alonso-Fradejas 2015); production plans (Diniz & Gilbert, 2013); credit unions (Hafild 2005); or certification labels (Paudel et al. 2010).

Promotion of community human capital

Two remarkable pathways have to do with the influence of movements on *social capital, community identity and community knowledge*. As reported in a fair number of cases. The reinforcement of community identity owes to an intrinsic linkage between resource use rights and political-cultural rights in many of the studied cases, especially in cases of indigenous communities. In the case of the "Pacific North Coast black communities" (PCN), much of the movement's success and impact on self-organization had to do with the elaboration of a discourse that mobilized critical issues of "place based" identity (Escobar 1998).

The participation of community members in movements' actions can also reinforce solidarity ties and trust. In the case of the anti-privatization mobilizations and the referendum promoted by community aqueduct activists in Colombia, Perera (2015) concludes that the referendum failed, but the "community water activists learned about each other, inspired each other, and developed trust" (pp. 205), creating capital for further collaboration in mobilizations and in commons management.

Similarly, movements can build on and promote *local traditional knowledge*. As per these cases, traditional knowledge is reproduced through at least three processes: (1) actual practices, like in the case of women's Green Belt Movement in Kenya (Brownhill, 2007; Turner & Brownhill, 2004); (2) educational and research campaigns, like in the case of the Dayak of Indonesia (Alcorn et al., 2003) and the *acequias* of the Rio Culebra in the US (Peña 2003); and (3) frames or narratives that legitimize said knowledge, like in the case of the PCN movement in Colombia (Escobar, 1998).

Improvement of community decision making

Also, social movements can contribute to the implementation and quality of collective decision making in the communities. First and foremost, they can *empower women*. In Bolivia, land reform movements' incorporated the recognition of women's land rights as one of their central demands, which led to legal prohibition of discrimination against women in access, tenancy, and inheritance of land and guarantee of women's access to land in the titling and redistribution process, irrespective of their marital status (Deere 2017). It also led to women achieving key leading political and elected positions and the creation of a legislative commission on women's.

Second, movements can lead or *promote deliberation* and self-reflective discussions (i.e., beyond just voting) about everyday issues as well as legal aspects, issues of community production practices and organizational capacity, as it happened with the Dayak movement in Indonesia (Alcorn et al. 2003) or the Afro-Colombian communities of the Pacific Coast (Escobar, 1998). Third, and closely related to the above, movements can enhance the *inclusiveness of decision-making* by opening spaces that give voice to the different social groups within the communities (Ojha 2011, Kenney-Lazar 2012, Diniz and Gilbert 2013, Martiniello 2015).

Finally, movements can support and promote the *formalization of previously informal decision-making processes* into collective-choice rules, through for instance the creation of community councils, community assemblies and other decision-making bodies (Oslender 2004, De Alessi 2012).

Enhancement of community organization capacities

Finally, grassroots development initiatives are often developed by movements in conjunction with the *promotion of community organizations and capacities*. For instance, the creation of extractive rubber-tapping reserves in Brazil was also based on the local organization of rubber tappers and on education, health, cooperativism, and resource management research programs (Diegues, 1998). Movements can also strengthen local organization through pedagogical strategies to educate about the meaning of new laws, founding concepts such as territory, development, traditional production, and use of natural resources (Alcorn et al., 2003; Escobar, 1998; Wouters, 2001); and promoting collaborations and exchanges of experiences among communities (Alcorn et al., 2003; Ojha, 2011).

A similarly relevant way of supporting communities is through the *creation of second-order community-organizations* for resource governance. For instance, the Colorado Acequia Association (CAA) in the Culebra watershed, U.S., was created to contest the enclosure of the commons as well as to find ways to guarantee the long-range viability of *acequia* farming. Accordingly, "the CAA defined its mission as to organize and conduct scientific and legal research to empower the *acequias* to manage and protect" said commons (Peña, 2003, pp. 163).

The Federation of Indigenous Organizations of Napo (FOIN), in the Ecuadorian Amazon, emerged as an effort by the movement to consolidate community rights and then evolved to integrate also forest management services for the communities (Cronkleton et al., 2008; Paudel, 2010; García-López and Antinori, 2018). In the case of fisheries, the Goenchea Ramponkarsancho Ekvott organization (GRE) was formed to protect the interests of traditional fishing communities in Goa, India; afterwards, aware of the powerful opponents they faced, and the similar threats faced by the millions of traditional fishermen in other parts of coastal India, the GRE promoted the creation of the National Forum for Catamaran and Country Boat Fishermen Rights and Marine Life (Somayaji, 2017).

Finally, movements assist the communities with *litigation resources*. These resources, which include expertise and legal training, as well as economic resources and coordination, allow the communities to address courts at governance levels otherwise inaccessible to them.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have addressed, via a meta-analysis of case studies, the question of whether and how community-based natural resource management (CBRNM) regimes are jeopardized by “decommonization” threats and the extent to which social movements contribute in turn to “commonization” in affected communities.

The evidence points to the notable impact of certain resource use and management “decommonization” drivers. These tend to concentrate in two big groups, including government (natural resource management and economic) policy and large-scale firms (e.g., mining, cultivations). Expectedly, the impact of these drivers both in the form of resource externalities such as scarcity and pollution and resource use and management right restrictions. Less expectedly and probably more importantly, the “decommonization” drivers also affect less tangible and resource-related “community essentials” such as cultural traits, social capital, and livelihoods. As pointed elsewhere, disconnection of people from their resources is indeed a major driver of “decommonization” (Nayak and Berkes 2011).

Also, the evidence points to a notable positive impact of the movements and CBRNM, and further underscores that these effects can occur through various pathways, enriching our understanding of “commonization” processes. Such impact has in many cases to do with the defense of community use and management rights against certain government decisions or actions by outside resource users. That said, movements can also generate positive spillovers independently from whether they are able or successful in fighting violations of community rights. Those “commonization spillovers” include the promotion of economic autonomy via, reinvigoration of community identity ties and social capital, the improvement of community decision making and the enhancement of community organizational capacity. Exploring whether these “commonization spillovers” involve longer-term effects is a promising question for further research.

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